

An original reconstruction of a full thickness defect secondary to a parietal invading bladder tumour

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ABSTRACT

Backgrounds: The reconstruction of large full-thickness abdominal wall defects usually requires microsurgical flaps. When microsurgery is not an option, the association of two pedicled flaps can be an alternative. This association is exceptionally reported in the literature. **Case:** We present the case of a 42 years old patient, with an invading bladder tumor. The tumorectomy resulted in a full thickness sub-umbilical wall defect. The large defect was reconstructed by the combination of a fasciocutaneous tensor fascia lata flap, associated with a Mc Gregor flap. Recovery was reached within 4 weeks, with minimal donor site sequelae. **Conclusion:** This case is an important addition to literature regarding a simple but original technique that can be used to manage full-thickness abdominal wall defects, especially when microsurgery is not available.

KEYWORDS abdominal wall, defect, fascia lata flap, Mc Gregor flap

INTRODUCTION

Many surgical techniques can be used to manage abdominal wall defects. The choice depends on several parameters: the defect surface, its extent, its location and the clinical context. [1] The tensor fascia lata flap (TFL) is often discussed in these cases [2; 3]. The authors present a case of reconstruction of a transfixing sub-umbilical abdominal wall defect by the original association of a classical TFL flap and a McGregor inguinal flap.

OBSERVATION:

We report the case of a patient who presented a parietal invading bladder tumour. He was 42 years old at the time, married with no children. He was a small boat fisherman with low income. On May 2012, this heavy smoker started to complain of lower abdominal pain and hematuria. (Figure1). An ultrasound exam revealed a large bladder stone. On January 2013, the patient was

operated on, in his small town hospital, by a general surgeon. During this first intervention, the surgeon discovered a vesical tumour. A biopsy was performed and revealed an invasive urothelial carcinoma. At this point, the general surgeon referred the patient to the university hospitals urology department. For social reasons (no health insurance, lack of education), the patient presented to our urology department seven months later. At this stage, clinical examination revealed an 8cm diameter hypogastric mass with an apparent parietal extension (Figure 2). The uroscanner showed a tumour of the bladder dome measuring 7x8 cm, with localized parietal invasion centred on the previous bladder incision. The urology team performed a radical cystoprostatectomy with monobloc resection of the overlying abdominal wall. To reconstruct the parietal defect, the two stages latissimus dorsi (LD) free flap "chausson au pommes" was the first logical option. However, given the toxic smoking habits and the reluctance of the patient towards a heavy two stages microsurgery, LD free flap was left aside. Considering the transfixing nature and the size of the defect (Figure 3), we opted for the association of two pedicled flaps: a McGregor flap and a fascio-cutaneous TFL flap. The neobladder was covered by an epiplooplasty and a non-absorbable mesh. The two flaps were sutured right on top of the synthetic mesh. The histological study of the resected specimen confirmed the wide and complete excision of the tumour.

Three days after surgery, the distal extremity of the fascia

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Figure 1: Timeline.

Figure 2: Preoperative view of the abdominal wall.

figure 3: the sub umbilical abdominal wall defect.

Figure 4: the patient, 4 weeks after surgery.

lata flap presented a limited venous stasis, to prevent necrosis and plaque exposure, we performed a minor revision surgery under local anaesthesia: the suffering area was excised, and the laxity of the rest of the flap allowed a direct closure without any tension. Complete healing was achieved after four weeks (Figure 4). The patient was referred to oncology for adjuvant chemotherapy. The patient was regularly seen for the last four years, by the oncologist, the plastic surgeon and the urologist: every two months in the first year, and every six months since then. No local recurrences or metastases were found. We proposed to remodel the flaps to improve the aesthetic outcome, but the patient declined and was satisfied with the result. Ten months after the intervention, and three months after the last chemotherapy session, he even resumed his usual activities (jogging, fishing). His main complaint though was related to the sexual dysfunction secondary to the radical cystoprostatectomy.

DISCUSSION

The management of large transfixing defects of the abdominal wall is always a challenge for plastic surgeons [4]. The reconstruction involves all the restorative techniques such as skin grafts, flaps, or skin expansion. It is possible to obtain a granulation tissue of the peritoneum or omentum especially after few days under a negative pressure therapy; a thin skin graft is then realizable. It is also possible in median defects to realize lateral cutaneous incisions and to mobilize two bi-pedicled flaps [1]. When the loss of substance is more important, the logical option is a free flap. The most suitable flap is the musculocutaneous latissimus dorsi flap which can be performed in one or two stages [5,6]. The mobilization of a free flap is a heavy technique, because of the hemorrhagic risk, the high rate of failure related to the risk of thrombosis of the vascular anastomoses and because it's usually a time-consuming procedure. Fascial reconstruction with a TFL flap is sometimes proposed, it is a musculocutaneous pedicled flap with a fascial component harvested from the lateral aspect of the thigh. [2,3] It is reliable, simple and easy to achieve. Its main drawbacks are the unaesthetic sequelae on the donor site, and a doubtful vascular reliability on its distal part, especially if the flap exceeds the lower third of the thigh. When the defect is large, beyond the coverage capacity of a single TFL flap, microsurgery is unavoidable. Indeed, it is generally advised to abstain from harvesting a TFL flap on both sides, because of the theoretical risk of knee instability. In some cases, microsurgery is not an option, therefore we can associate another pedicled flap. The anterolateral thigh perforating flap (ALT) was initially described by Song et al. in 1984 [7]. It is a perforating, fasciocutaneous flap raised as an island, based on the existence of a branch of the descending artery of the lateral circumflex femoral artery [1]. The pedicled ALT flap enables satisfactory reconstruction of large abdominal wall defects [8]. Its dissection can be tedious to inexperienced hands which can significantly prolong the operation [9]. In our case, we chose to associate a TFL flap and a pedicled Mc Gregor flap. This cutaneous axial flap based on the superficial circumflex iliac vessels was described by Mc Gregor in 1972 and has since proved his worth. This flap is simple to dissect, it offers a large cutaneous surface that can be harvested, and a direct closure of the donor site is often possible with easily concealed scars. This association was not the first choice, a free LD flap, a pedicled or a free ALT would have been the obvious solution for this defect. But given the psychological profile of the patient (refused microsurgery, couldn't stop smoking), and the 4 hours taken by the urologists

(to perform a radical cystectomy, a bilateral pelvic lymph node dissection, and a neo cystoplasty), we opted for the combination of two easy, quick and reliable flaps: a McGregor and a TFL flap. The Placement of a synthetic mesh beneath the solid fascia lata aponeurosis assured a satisfactory parietal resistance for a young active subject.

CONCLUSION:

The combination of the TFL flap and the inguinal flap can be very interesting for the reconstruction of full-thickness sub umbilical abdominal wall defects. When free flaps are contraindicated or in the absence of a microsurgical platform, the combination of these two flaps offers an excellent alternative. This case report will be a valuable addition to literature regarding the management of similar cases especially because this combination is easily reproducible and can be life-saving in humanitarian missions or unplanned emergency reconstructions.

Authors' Statements

Competing Interests The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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